

Towards the next generation of high-performance Li-ion battery cells

WORK PACKAGE 1 (WP1)

D1.2 Data Management Plan Update (V2.0)

Lead Contractor: SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS (SIE).

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This document is the NEXTCELL project Data Management Plan Update (V2.0) (contract no. 101069910) corresponding to D1.2 (M18) led by SIE.

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Acronyms and abbreviations

DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
M	Project Month
OA	Open Access
OS	Open Science
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This report is the NEXTCELL project **D1.2 – Data Management Plan Update**, due in M18.

As part of this innovative project, a comprehensive Data Management Plan (DMP) has been developed to ensure the effective collection, storage, sharing, and preservation of data generated throughout the project lifecycle. This report outlines the strategies, policies, and procedures that will be implemented to maximize the value and impact of the project's data while adhering to ethical, legal, and regulatory requirements.

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1. Introduction

The battery cells currently available on the market are made up of solid (electrodes, separators) and liquid (electrolyte) components. To create the next generation of high-performance lithium (Li)-ion battery cells, NEXTCELL (a consortium of 17 partners from 10 different European nations) will spend 48 months developing and validating a revolutionary gellified cell concept. This concept incorporates several material-level innovations for each of the key cell components, including the gellification of the electrodes and separator in conjunction with a high voltage-stable gel electrolyte.

The project's prototyped cells will therefore have a high energy density and operate very well in high power applications. In addition to offering cutting-edge cells to the European market, NEXTCELL will also address three crucial issues including prices, safety, and sustainability, that now prevent Li-ion battery technology from being used more widely.

In this regard, NEXTCELL's technology will firstly optimize the production processes, lowering the capital and operating expenses of future gigafactories by skipping the electrolyte filling stage and solvent evaporation. Secondly, the initiative will create intrinsically safe cells by eliminating the use of separator and electrolytes that have low boiling points. Finally, an energy consumption reduction of 50% will be assured.

Regarding WP1 and this report, the focus of the **Data Management Plan (DMP)** is to ensure that the project complies with **(1) the FAIR data principles** (making data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable), and **(2) GDPR**, regulation that went into effect in May 2018 with the goal of protecting and empowering all EU citizens' personal data privacy and reshaping the way organizations manage data.

According to the guidelines provided by Horizon Europe regarding the development of a DMP, the final version of this report will include **(1)** the methods to handle the research data during and after the project's end, **(2)** descriptions of the datasets that will be collected, processed, and/or generated, **(3)** methodologies and standards adopted for the data management, **(4)** the level of accessibility/confidentiality of the data, and **(5)** methods to curate and preserve the data during the project.

2. Purpose of data generation and collection

The project's data collection will centre around the prototyping of the gellified concept, which will include feeding and sourcing data from other dimensions of the project, such as modelling and simulation and the evaluation of technical, safety, environmental sustainability, and cost improvements.

This data will include information and knowledge produced and obtained during the project lifetime, including the development of material and cell components, small and large-scale gellified cells, development of a multi-scale and multi-physic porous electrode-based performance model, as well as the evaluation of cell technical performance, safety, and sustainability – environmental and cost analysis.

In addition, personal data will be collected for the effective communication and dissemination of the project outcomes, such as: newsletters and project communications distribution, invitation to relevant events, among others.

3. Data generation and collection methodology

The data collected during the project lifetime will be gathered in the form of questionnaires, surveys, webinars, newsletters, testing and modelling activities, prototyping activities, among others. This information will be logged and classified in a living document titled "NEXTCELL_Data repository" located in the project's SharePoint (WP1 folder) where partners will add and/or update any new datasets generated in the project, following SIE's indications.

The template to be used for the data repository has been created by SIE following the Horizon Europe guidelines for data management and is shown in the table below.

Table 1: NEXTCELL's dataset description template

NEXTCELL's data trackrecord	
Data Set Indicator	Indicator number within the project (dataset 1, dataset 2... dataset n)
Data Set Name	Name of dataset
Relation to WP/tasks	WP number and task number dataset is related to
IPR Owner	Data owner (organization)
Data Collector	Organization collecting the data
Data Summary	
Persistent Identifier	Long-lasting reference to a digital resource (e.g. ORCID ID). An identifier is a label which gives a unique name to an entity: a person, place, or thing. Unlike URLs, which may break, a persistent identifier reliably points to a digital entity
Data Source	Re-use of existing data or original data
Data Set Description	Brief description of the contents in the dataset, including relation to the project
Category Type	E.g.: experimental data, publication, personal data, etc
Data Format	E.g.: .docx, .ppt, .xlsx, etc
Size	Approximate size of file (or files)
Number of files	Number of files

	Data utility	Who might find this data useful?
Data Findability	Keywords	Short keywords to facilitate others to find and re-use this data
	Metadata and standards	Is there use of metadata for the generation of this dataset?
	Will the data be archived in an external repository?	Yes/No, which one (e.g. ZENODO)
	If yes, what's the object identifier	DOI
Data Accessibility	Access level	Public, restricted, private, mixed
	Requirements of access	Any special software/methods to access information?
	Availability for sharing	Yes/No/Restricted access
	Reasons for not sharing	If the data cannot be shared, state briefly why (e.g.: confidentiality to keep competitive advantage, etc)
	Embargo date	In case the data cannot be published yet, but is expected to be made available publicly after a certain amount of time
	Procedure for sharing	In case it can be shared but under certain conditions, explain those conditions
	Ethical/legal impacts of sharing	Any potential ethical or legal aspects to consider for sharing
Period of time of preservation	For how long you are planning to store the data?	
Data Interoperability	Use of standard vocabularies	If yes, what kind? (e.g. business terms)
	References to other data	Yes/No, if yes, mention which data you are referencing
Data Re-use	Will data be freely available in the public domain?	Yes/No
	Will data be re-usable for other third parties after the end of the project?	Yes/No
	Procedures to ensure data quality	What procedures are in place in your organization to ensure data quality?

Procedures to ensure data archiving, preservation, and security	What procedures are in place in your organization to ensure archiving, preservation, and security of data?
Where will the data be preserved?	Which "repository" will your data be archived in? (e.g. internal repository, ZENODO, etc)
Associated costs	Any associated costs with data preservation

When made available, the public datasets will be published in OpenAire (or any other trustworthy public repository) and will also be included in the SEDIA platform as knowledge produced by the project, in accordance with the open science (OS) policy of the Horizon Europe program which calls for *"making data as open as possible, and as closed as necessary."*

The decision and definition of the conditions and requirements for sharing these datasets will be made by the data owner (respective project partner). Some datasets might not be available for sharing due to limitations imposed for ethical, IPR, and/or commercial exploitation reasons. The project datasets marked as confidential will be treated as sensible information and will not be shared unless specifically authorized by the owning party.

NEXTCELL's data repository was set in order to keep track of the data generation and collection, and to report any limitations on their potential re-use by third parties. The project partners in charge of each dataset will update and amend the content as necessary. SIE will serve as data protection officer, reminding the beneficiaries to review the repository every six months in order to keep the information up to date.

4. Making NEXTCELL's data FAIR

The need for maintaining data FAIR is emphasized in the DMP recommendations from the European Commission (GDPR, 2020). NEXTCELL project endorses the FAIR data policy to ensure that the datasets created and gathered in the project will conform with said policy.

4.1. Making data FINDABLE

Including data in an open repository is the recommended practice for all Horizon Europe project following the OS approach. When speaking about articles and papers, a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be used as unique code to identify the article and journal where it has been published in. Nevertheless, datasets are not limited to papers or articles, they can include all type of data produced during the project lifetime, excel files, reports, databases, testing results, among many others.

For the purposes of maintaining all data cohesive, a naming convention and style is determined in this report, done with the objective of making all documents more coherent and easier to find, making the names include the important information of the document.

The convention to be used in the NEXTCELL project will follow the table below.

Table 2: Naming convention to be used during the project

NEXTCELL's file naming convention	
"NEXTCELL"	Project Name
"WPX"	Related work package number, e.g. "WP1" for work package 1
"TX.Y"	Task number, e.g. "T1.1" for task 1.1
"DX.Y"	Deliverable number, eg. D1.1
"Title"	Short description of the document
"Version"	Version number, e.g. "v1.0" for first version
"Date"	Date in "DDMMYY" format

In this way, all files must be named following example: "ProjectName_WPX_TX.Y_DX.Y_Title_Version_Date," they must be stored in the corresponding WP and task subfolder in the project SharePoint. In this way, if one were to

name Deliverable 1.2 (this report) the name should be as follows: "NEXTCELL_WP1_T1.5_D1.2_Data Management Plan Update_v2.0_28062024" and it should be stored in WP1 > Task1.5 subfolder.

4.2. Making data ACCESSIBLE

In reference to Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, **each beneficiary is responsible for disseminating the project's results as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public via appropriate means, with the only exception to this being having their legitimate interests infringed by doing it.**

The NEXTCELL projects follows the OS approach, which requires partners to:

- Procure the maximum openness possible of the project results, as long as it does not interfere with the safekeeping of their IP.
- Involve several stakeholders in project activities to identify any requirements and/or to identify bottlenecks for market uptake or scale-up.
- Participate in the scientific dimension and in general communication and dissemination activities with other key EU initiatives.

In order to comply with this approach, **the project partners must ensure open access (OA) to the scientific publications related to their research outputs**, also specified in Article 17 of the GA.

For this purpose, beneficiaries are recommended to opt for:

- **Green open access:** where the author deposits the manuscript in either institutional repositories or other repositories with immediate or delayed OA, where the publications are accessible for free to any user.
- **Gold open access:** the author publishes the work in an OA journal or book, supported by an OA publisher. The rules of publication are the same as with traditional publishers, with the exception that the public can access the published material without charge. Although it should be emphasized that an increasing number of OA publishers waive these fees, the gold open access does not charge the reader and transfers the costs of article processing charges (APCs) to the author. **Related costs to procure gold open access are eligible only if the platform is fully OA, meaning that hybrid journals (with some articles OA and other subscription limited) are the exception.**

Another potential option for an OA repository is publishing via the Open Research Europe platform¹, created by the EC and intended for the publication of research generated in H2020 and Horizon Europe programs (European Commission, 2022).

¹ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/publish-your-research>

4.3. Making data INTEROPERABLE

Describing, collecting, and storing data in a consistent way will ensure that the data produced during the NEXTCELL project is easy to re-use across project beneficiaries and external parties, when possible.

Regarding the dissemination of data and project results, all involved partners must be notified with at least a 15-days' notice before the dissemination takes place, this of course applies to the content reported in the data repository of the project, and to any other material produced. Other beneficiaries may object within the 15 days by providing proper justification, including the reason of infringement of their legitimate interests. If the conflict cannot be solved, the dissemination would not be able to take place.

4.4. Making data REUSABLE

The datasets generated during the project's lifetime are intended to be highly re-usable, with the intention of collaborating with further research on the battery cell field and its related innovations. As mentioned before, the project is also under the OS approach, meaning that all datasets marked as available for sharing by the respective owning beneficiary will be published as soon as possible to ensure interested stakeholders can freely access their contents.

To achieve the reusability of the data, the datasets must be sufficiently and correctly described so machine and human users can determine if the identified data is what they are looking for. This can be achieved by following data standardization practices, providing clear terms for data reuse, and ensuring interoperability of the data.

5. Data security

The NEXTCELL consortium uses Microsoft Teams and SharePoint as a platform for the storage and exchange of data and materials relevant to the project. Built on the hyper-scale, enterprise-grade cloud infrastructure of Microsoft 365 and Office 365, Microsoft Teams offers sophisticated security and compliance features (Microsoft, n.d.).

Microsoft Teams supports two-factor authentication for the entire team and organization, an active directory single sign-on, and data encryption both in transit and at rest. Applications like SharePoint and OneNote integrate with Teams for content management. SharePoint encryption is used to protect files while they are being stored there, and OneNote encryption is used to protect the notes created (Microsoft, n.d.).

Account holders tend to be the weaker link in the system when it comes to security risks. The following are some best-practice procedures to have in mind to guarantee the security of the project data, among them: **(1)** create a secure password that is distinct from those for other accounts, **(2)** if you share a computer with someone else, sign out of your account when you are finished, **(3)** do not install Microsoft Teams on a shared or public computer, this would put your files at risk of being accessed by other users, and **(4)** use two-step verification as an additional layer of security to deter hackers.

6. Ethical aspects

The Article 14 of the GA specifies the Ethics and Values that must be followed throughout the project, specifically regarding:

- Ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity and applicable international, EU, and national law).
- Values (commitment to the basic EU values, such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, and human rights).

As already mentioned, the NEXTCELL project will store personal data at both the regional and pan-European levels for communication and dissemination reasons. In some cases, specific original national data protection laws may be applicable, but the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) will always be regarded as the primary data protection law. GDPR aims to protect and empower all EU citizens' personal data privacy as well as to reshape the way organizations across the region manage data and proceed towards data privacy, for this, it is organized around seven key principles (GDPR EU, 2018):

- **Lawfulness, fairness, and transparency:** the processing of the data must be lawful, fair, and transparent to the data subject.
- **Purpose limitation:** data must be processed for the legitimate purposes specified to the data subject before collection.
- **Data minimization:** you must collect and process only the necessary data for the specified purposes.
- **Accuracy:** personal data must be kept accurate and up to date.
- **Storage limitation:** the time to store data must be only for as long as necessary for the specified purpose.
- **Integrity and confidentiality:** the necessary steps must be taken so the processing of the data is done with integrity, in a secure and confidential manner.
- **Accountability:** the data controller is responsible for being able to demonstrate GDPR compliance.

Personal data is information that can identify an individual (name, number, location, IP address, etc.). However, for the purposes of GDPR, information that has had identifiers removed or substituted to make the data anonymous is still considered personal data (European Commission, 2018).

Therefore, the responsible partner should be aware of the GDPR requirements and make sure to comply with the legislation if any dataset generated or collected as part of the NEXTCELL project has data privacy issues (GDPR, 2020). The consortium is required to adhere to the following GDPR rules when relevant (GDPR EU, 2018):

- ✓ **Conditions for consent:**
The request for consent, along with the justification for data processing linked to that consent, must be made in a clear and clearly understandable manner. Clear and plain wording must be utilized rather than complex terms or conditions.
- ✓ **Increased territorial scope:**
GDPR is applicable if at least one of the following conditions is met:
 - Personal data processing concerns data subjects in the EU.

- The personal data controller or processor is based in the EU, regardless of the exact location of processing taking place.

✓ **Data subject rights:**

- **Breach notification:** In case of any data breach that may result in a risk for the rights and freedoms of an individual, the breach notification must be provided within 72 hours after becoming aware of a data breach.
- **Right to access:** Data subjects are empowered to request confirmation with the data controller that if personal data concerning them is being processed, where and for what purpose, and they shall receive an electronic copy of personal data without additional cost.
- **Right to rectification:** right to have inaccurate personal data rectified.
- **Right to restrict processing:** right to restrict the processing of their personal data in certain circumstances.
- **Right to data portability:** right to receive personal data provided to a controller in a structured, machine-readable format.
- **Right to be forgotten** data subjects have the right to demand the data controller to erase their personal data, cease further dissemination, and halt third-parties processing it upon condition that the data is no longer applicable for the original purpose, or the data subjects withdraw their consents.
- **Privacy by design:** data controller shall include data protection into consideration from the very beginning of designing of systems. Appropriate measures shall be taken to protect the rights of data subjects, for instance only data which is considered necessary for completion of the tasks should be held and processed and only relevant personnel would be granted the access rights for data processing.
- **Right to be informed:**
 - Inform individuals about the collection and use of their personal data.
 - Individuals should be informed of the following: Why their personal data is being processed, how long it will be kept, and with whom it will be shared. It is called the “privacy information.”
 - Provide the privacy information to individuals at the time their personal data are collected from them.
 - When you obtain personal data from a source other than the individual, you need to provide the individual with privacy information in less than a month. If you use data to communicate with the individual, you should provide privacy information at the latest when the first communication takes place.

- When you collect personal data from the individual it relates to, you must provide them with privacy information at the time you obtain their data, you must tell people who you are giving their information to and give them an easy solution to opt out.
- The information you provide to people must be concise, transparent, intelligible, easily accessible, and it must use clear and plain language.
- It is often most effective to provide the privacy information to people using a combination of different techniques including layering, dashboards, and just-in-time notices.
- User testing is an effective way to get feedback on how effective the delivery of your privacy information is.
- You must regularly review, and where necessary, update your privacy information. You must bring any new uses of an individual's personal data to their attention before you start the processing.

The following checklist must be followed in order to properly inform parties on the reason for collection of information and on who will be responsible for said data.

Table 3: Checklist for GDPR compliance

What information do we need to provide?	What should we tell people?	When is it required?
The name and contact details of your organization	Say who you are and how individuals can contact you.	Always
The name and contact details of your representative	Say who your representative is and how to contact them (a representative is an organization that represents you if you are based outside the EU, but you monitor or offer services to people in the EU).	If applicable
The contact details of your data protection officer	Say how to contact your data protection officer (DPO) (certain organizations are required to appoint a DPO).	If applicable
The purposes of the processing	Explain why you use people's personal data. Be clear about each different purpose (there are many different reasons for using personal data, you will know best the reasons why you use data. Typical purposes could include marketing, order processing and staff administration).	Always
The lawful basis for the processing	Explain which lawful basis you are relying on in order to collect and use people's personal data and/or special category data.	Always
The legitimate interests for the processing	Explain what the legitimate interests for the processing are.	If applicable
The recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data	Say who you share people's personal data with. This includes anyone that processes the personal data on your behalf, as well all other organizations. Be as specific as	If applicable

	possible if you only tell people the categories of organizations.	
The details of transfers of the personal data to any third countries or international organizations	Tell people if you transfer their personal data to any countries or organizations outside the EU.	If applicable
The retention periods for the personal data	Say how long you will keep the personal data for. If you do not have a specific retention period, then you need to tell people the criteria you use to decide how long you will keep their information.	Always
The rights available to individuals in respect of the processing	Tell people which rights they have in relation to your use of their personal data, e.g. access, rectification, erasure, restriction, objection, and data portability. The rights will differ depending on the lawful basis for processing – make sure what you tell people accurately reflects this. The right to object must be explicitly brought to people’s attention clearly and separately from any other information.	Always
The right to withdraw consent	Let people know that they can withdraw their consent for your processing of their personal data at any time. Consent must be as easy to withdraw as it is to give. Tell people how they can do this.	If applicable
The right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority	Tell people that they can complain to a supervisory authority. Each EU Member State has a designated data protection supervisory authority. Individuals have the right to raise a complaint with the supervisory authority in the Member State where they live, where they work, or where the infringement took place.	Always
The details of whether individuals are under a statutory or contractual obligation to provide the personal data	Tell people if they are required by law, or under contract, to provide personal data to you, and what will happen if they do not provide that data. Often, this will only apply to some, and not all, of the information being collected. You should be clear with individuals about the specific types of personal data that are required under a statutory or contractual obligation.	If applicable

The details of the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling

Say whether you make decisions based solely on automated processing, including profiling, that have legal or similarly significant effects on individuals. Give people meaningful information about the logic involved in the process and explain the significance and envisaged consequences.

If applicable

7. Allocation of resources

If the conditions in Article 6 of the Grant Agreement (for eligibility conditions) are satisfied, costs associated with the OA of research data in the Horizon Europe program may be reimbursed during the project's lifetime. This is provided that the publishing is done in an OA repository or journal, and as it was already established, this implies that hybrid journals (those that provide both subscription and OA options) are not eligible.

According to the Grant Agreement, there is no funding allocated for data management after the project lifetime. The long-term preservation of data in the NEXTCELL project will depend on the ability of the beneficiaries in the consortium to continue working together on the same file-sharing platform (Microsoft Teams).

The license agreement associated with the public repository where the data will be placed shall be followed in all cases of data sharing and re-use (such as Creative Commons, Open Data Commons) after publication. By downloading the data, the user accepts full responsibility for its terms of use. The data collected and stored through NEXTCELL will also be made available to other parties through peer-reviewed OA publications, seminars, and conferences, in accordance with the distribution criteria.

8. Public Repository Use Protocol

The public repository to be used to publish the NEXTCELL project main research results will be Open Research Europe, this open repository serves as a freely accessible publishing platform designed for disseminating research outcomes supported by funding from Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, and/or Euratom, spanning various fields of study. This platform simplifies adherence to the open access requirements stipulated by these funding programs, providing beneficiaries with a convenient avenue to share their findings swiftly. Moreover, it offers researchers a venue to swiftly disseminate their findings, fostering an environment conducive to open and constructive discourse within the research community (Open Research Europe, 2024).

8.1. Open Research Europe Policies

Open Research Europe policies provide the standards for the submission of articles, among the main policies are the following.

8.1.1. Publication Criteria

At least one author must be affiliated with an ongoing or completed project under Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, or Euratom from the European Commission, and the article must derive from that project.

The article must be original work.

There are no publication fees for beneficiaries of Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, and Euratom, as all costs are covered by the European Commission.

8.1.2. Originality

All submissions to Open Research Europe must be entirely original, without prior publication or consideration elsewhere. Any significant overlap with other works must be disclosed and cited upon submission. Plagiarism, including self-plagiarism, results in immediate rejection upon detection during plagiarism checks.

Articles previously shared on preprint servers like ArXiv, SSRN, bioRxiv, or MedRxiv are eligible for submission.

Content violating copyright may lead to rejection unless offending sections are removed. Authors intending to reproduce figures or tables from copyrighted sources must secure permission and provide proper attribution. Figures under a Creative Commons license may be reused according to their specific terms.

8.1.3. Authorship

Authors must have contributed significantly to the article's development, following the authorship criteria outlined by the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE). Each author's contribution must be specified using CRediT roles during submission.

Individuals who contributed but don't meet authorship criteria, such as technical or writing assistance, should be acknowledged. Any professional assistance from scientific or medical writers must be disclosed, with permission obtained for inclusion in acknowledgments.

The use of AI tools like large language models (LLMs) for content generation doesn't align with ORE authorship standards. Authors are solely responsible for the originality, validity, and integrity of their submissions. Any assistance from AI tools must be acknowledged within the article, and authors are expected to use such tools responsibly and in line with ORE editorial policies and publishing ethics principles.

8.1.4. Competing Interests

Authors must provide a "Competing interests" statement for transparency, even if there are none, in which case the standard statement "No competing interests were disclosed" is used. Competing interests can be financial or non-financial, including affiliations with organizations benefiting from the publication, holding patents, or having ideological affiliations. Authors from sponsoring commercial entities must declare their affiliations. Open Research Europe prohibits content advertising commercial products. Reviewers and readers must also disclose any competing interests.

8.1.5. Ethical Policies

Research published in Open Research Europe must adhere to ethics and integrity guidelines outlined in Article 14 of the Model Grant Agreement of Horizon Europe (Same Article in NEXTCELL GA – 101069910). This includes completing the Ethics Issues Table during proposal submission and undergoing additional ethics checks for certain topics like involvement of vulnerable populations or use of human stem cells. Authors must ensure compliance with European and national laws, including obtaining necessary ethics approvals. Failure to comply will result in rejection of submissions.

8.1.6. Data Availability

Open Research Europe follows Horizon Europe's open access policy for research data, aiming for openness while respecting necessary restrictions. Authors of original publications must deposit supporting research data in a trusted repository, accessible under specific licenses. Failure to provide justified data access leads to rejection.

Authors must ensure data replicability and provide details of tools used. A Data Availability Statement is mandatory. For comprehensive guidelines on data inclusion, storage, and presentation, refer to our Data Guidelines. Exceptions to open data are permitted in line with Horizon Europe policies, including commercial interests, privacy, and legal obligations. Authors should inform the editorial team of such exceptions during submission. All shared data should be in English.

8.1.7. Licenses

Open Research Europe advocates immediate open access to promote global knowledge exchange. Articles are typically published under a CC BY license, allowing unrestricted use with proper citation while maintaining the copyright with the author or institution. Associated data are shared under a CCo license when feasible, promoting reuse and addressing attribution issues. Peer reviews are also available under the CC BY license (Open Research Europe, 2024).

Additional information on all the Open Research Europe Policies can be found in the following link: [Policies | Open Research Europe \(europa.eu\)](#).

8.2. Project Internal Pre-submission Process

The project internal pre-submission process for the research articles produced during the project lifetime will be as follows:

Draft Document Preparation:

Before initiating the submission process, researchers within the project consortium develop a draft document with the research findings. This draft encompasses the results obtained from the project's activities.

Include Document and Datasets Used in the DMP Repository:

Include the document and its references to any datasets utilized in the research, in the Data Management Plan (DMP) repository. In the persistent identifier section indicate that will be defined after publication.

Internal Review by Partners within the same WP:

The draft document undergoes an internal review process conducted by partners involved in the same WP. This internal review aims to ensure the accuracy, coherence, and relevance of the research findings presented in the draft. Partners provide feedback, suggestions for improvement, and identify any discrepancies or areas requiring clarification.

External Review by Partners from Other WPs with Expertise in Similar Areas:

Following the internal review, the draft document is subjected to an external review by partners from other WPs who possess expertise in similar research areas. These external reviewers offer a fresh perspective and in-depth evaluation of the research content. They provide constructive criticism, validate the methodologies employed, and assess the significance of the findings within the broader context of the project's objectives.

Coordinator Approval:

Upon completion of the internal and external reviews, the draft document, along with the feedback received, is submitted to the project coordinator for approval. The coordinator evaluates the recommendations provided by the reviewers, ensuring that any suggested revisions align with the project's goals and objectives. Following thorough consideration, the coordinator provides approval for proceeding with the submission process to ORE.

Approval Request to All Consortium Partners:

Once the coordinator grants approval, an official request for approval is circulated to all consortium partners. This request includes the revised draft document, incorporating the suggested changes from both internal and external reviewers. Consortium partners are encouraged to review the document and provide their final approval before submission to ORE.

Start ORE Submission Process:

Upon receiving unanimous approval from all consortium partners, the ORE submission process is initiated. Researchers upload the finalized manuscript to the ORE online submission system, ensuring that all relevant metadata, including project title, funding information, and dataset references, are accurately provided. The submission signifies the culmination of the internal pre-submission process and marks the beginning of the formal publication process on Open Research Europe.

8.3. ORE Submission Process

In general, the submission process of ORE encompasses the following steps:

Submission System:

Research can be submitted through ORE's streamlined single-page submission system. Authors should refer to the Article Guidelines for specific instructions on submitting different types of articles. Progress of submissions can be monitored through the author's My Account page.

Prepublication Review:

ORE's team of professional editors conducts thorough prepublication checks to ensure compliance with all policies and ethical guidelines. Authors can find more information about these checks and the associated requirements.

Publication and Data Deposition:

Upon successful completion of prepublication checks, the article is published in a fully typeset version with a DOI, enabling immediate viewing, citation, and indexing in Google Scholar. Once published, the article cannot be

submitted to another journal for review and publication. The new DOI must be included in the persistent identifier section of the DMP repository.

Open Peer Review and Article Revision:

Expert reviewers are carefully selected and invited to review articles. Their reviews, along with their names, are published alongside the article, along with responses from the authors and comments from registered users.

Submission to Indexers and Repositories:

Authors are encouraged to publish revised versions of their articles. All versions of an article are linked and independently citable. Articles that pass peer review are indexed in external databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar (Open Research Europe, 2024).

Additional information on the ORE submission process can be found in [How it Works | Open Research Europe \(europa.eu\)](#).

9. Project Data Summary (M18)

Table 4 introduces the first section of the NECTCELL DMP Data Repository, which identifies the data set name, owners, collectors, data identifiers and sources, formats, among other elements of the data. Additional components of this tool can be found in the raw file on the project's SharePoint.

Table 4: Project Data Summary (M18).

Data Set Indicator	Data Set Name	Relation to WP/Tasks	IPR Owner	Data Collector	Persistent Identifier	Data Source	Data Set Description & Relation to Project	Category Type	Data Format	Size	Number of files	Data Utility
1	Exploitation Plan Questionnaires	WP9, Task 9.2 & 9.3	SIE & all partners	SIE	No	Original, no use of existing data	This dataset includes all the questionnaires answered by each partner in the consortium for the information about the KERs, market analysis, IP and exploitation	Technical description of the KER as well as some relevant business information	Word	Around 10MB	16	Partners within the consortium
2	Abuse tests	WP5	THI	THI	Not defined	Original	data files, photos, videos	Experimental data	Word, excel, JPG, and MP4	In GBs	Not defined	Project partners
3	Personal data for Newsletter	WP9 T9.1	SIE & all partners	SIE	No	Original	Email addresses were collected for newsletter subscription through NEXTCELL's Website. Email address of SMEs and Energy Experts who signed up and expressed their interest in NEXTCELL project.	Personal data/contact information	Mailchimp audience list	N/A	N/A	Partners within the consortium
4	Software tools to reach dissemination targets	WP9 T9.1	SIE & all partners	SIE	No	Original	Website, videos and other digital tools developed to reach the target of the WP	Communication materials	PPT, PDF, JPEG, PNG, video, website	Around 1 Gb	8	Partners within the consortium, targeted audiences

5	Financial statements partners	WP1 T1.2	SIE & all partners	SIE	No	Original	Financial statements provided by partners during the official reporting periods and intermediate ones	Project data	Excel	500MB	18	Analise project financial progress
6	Modelling data	WP7, T7.2	UL	UL	No	Original, no use of existing data	Output results of the aging model and phase-field model	Modelling results	Simple human-readable format, e.g. .txt, .csv, .dat file	Approx. in range of GB	approx. 100	Project partners
7	Cycling tests and ageing protocols	WP5, Task 5.1, 5.2, 5.3	WP5 partners	POLITO, UPV, THI	No	Original, no use of existing data	data files, images		word, excel, pdf	In GBs	n.d.	Partners within the consortium
8	Characterization of thermal degradation of cell components	WP7, T7.3	All partners	UPV	No	Original, no use of existing data	data files	Experimental data	Excel	1Gb	1	Partners within the consortium
9	Technical data package	WP3	Umicore	Not defined	No	Original	This dataset shows basic characterization of the Umicore proprietary cathode material sent for integration	experimental data	PDF	1	1	Partners integrating the UCAM in the consortium

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10. Conclusions

This report summarises the second version of NEXTCELL's DMP, establishing the methodology to follow regarding data collection, processing, and preservation, as well as the best practices to ensure data security and to comply with the open science approach, the latter with clear protocols that aim to ensure openness of research results within the project.

The purpose of data management is to ensure that data collection is done properly and to standardize its use and reuse throughout the project and after. The generated data will be compiled into datasets and logged in accordance with the instructions provided on this deliverable.

The project's outcomes will be presented as Key Exploitable Results (KER), and their exploitation following the project will take the consortium's interests, IP background, IPR landscape, and foreground into consideration, which must all be in line with data management practices.

11. References

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